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Enhanced multi-mission remote sensing of inland water surface elevation using Sentinel-3, Sentinel-6, and SWOT satellite altimeters and an environmentally informed LSTM-based neural network

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ABSTRACT

Frequent and accurate measurements of inland Water Surface Elevation (WSE) are essential for effective water resource management. However, single-mission satellite altimetry often lacks the temporal resolution needed to capture detailed WSE changes. While multi-mission integration can improve temporal coverage, it is hindered by inter- and intra-mission biases arising from variations in sensor design, orbital characteristics, atmospheric effects, and environmental conditions. These biases, which have been insufficiently addressed in previous studies, are typically nonlinear, spatiotemporally variable, and require advanced methods for correction. This study proposes EILSTMNet, an Environmentally Informed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)-based Neural Network that enables multi-mission synergy of satellite altimetry data (Sentinel-3, Sentinel-6, and SWOT) by correcting altimetric measurements of WSE through the integration of environmental variables such as precipitation, temperature, and evapotranspiration. EILSTMNet employs stacked LSTM layers to capture temporal dependencies in environmental drivers, combined with a fully connected neural network that incorporates static inputs such as altimetric WSE, day of year, and satellite-specific identifiers. The proposed approach is validated over three U.S. lakes, Michigan, Ontario, and Winnebago, using in-situ gauge measurements. Results show that EILSTMNet-based estimates are significantly improved compared to altimeter-derived WSE measurements, reducing the Root Mean Squared Error from 0.31 m to 0.09 m and increasing the Pearson correlation coefficient from 0.69 to 0.93. Furthermore, the model demonstrates strong generalization to unseen time periods, highlighting its temporal transferability. The proposed approach refines multi-mission altimetric measurements, yielding temporally frequent, higher-

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accuracy WSE observations, thereby enhancing water resource management and advancing the understanding of hydrological processes.

1. Introduction

Monitoring inland Surface Water Resources (SWRs) under climate change and anthropogenic pressures has become increasingly urgent (Taheri Dehkordi et al., 2022; Woolway et al., 2020). To this end, continuous measurements of Water Surface Elevation (WSE) have traditionally been conducted through in-situ gauge stations (hereafter referred to as $WSE_{in-situ}$); however, these stations are often spatially sparse and costly to maintain (Tauro et al., 2018). Satellite radar altimetry has emerged as a powerful Remote Sensing (RS) technique by providing global and frequent observations (Jaramillo et al., 2024).

The individual revisit times of the latest generation of satellite radar altimetry missions, such as 27 days for Sentinel-3 (S3), 10 days for Sentinel-6 (S6), and 21 days for Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT), are insufficient for capturing the rapid dynamics of WSE when used in single-mission scenarios (Yao et al., 2025). Integrating the data from multiple missions enhances observation frequency of WSE (Tarpanelli and Benveniste, 2019). However, each satellite altimeter is characterized by distinct technical specifications and varying levels of measurement accuracy, making them inherently inconsistent data sources (Feng et al., 2023). To enable effective multi-mission monitoring of WSE, it is essential to correct altimeter-derived WSE values (hereafter referred to as WSE_{alt}) for both inter-mission biases (differences between missions) and intra-mission biases (inconsistencies within a single-mission) (Riçko et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2011). These biases are not uniform and can vary significantly across both space and time. Inter-mission biases typically arise from differences in sensor design, orbital configuration, reference datums, and processing algorithms, including retracking methods as well as geophysical and atmospheric correction models (Bosch et al., 2014). Intra-mission biases, on the other hand, may result from environmental influences, atmospheric variability, and temporal changes in data quality (Fernandes and Lázaro, 2016).

Previous studies have mostly overlooked the inter- and intra-mission biases (Normandin et al., 2024). In contrast, some studies have computed an average bias during overlapping periods or from simultaneous measurements and applying it to the entire time series (Aminjafari et al., 2024; Feng et al., 2023; L. Jiang et al., 2023; Maubant et al., 2025; Schröder et al., 2019). This strategy requires substantial temporal overlap to account for spatiotemporal variability of biases (Huang et al., 2023). Moreover, it primarily

Fig. 1. (a) Locations of the three target inland lakes in this study; (b) Lake Winnebago; (c) Lake Michigan; and (d) Lake Ontario. Panels (b), (c), and (d) also show the locations of USGS in-situ gauge stations (red triangles) as well as the ground tracks of the S3, S6, and SWOT missions.

considers inter-mission biases and implicitly assumes a reference mission free of intra-mission biases (Zhang et al., 2025). This assumption is not valid given the influences of local topography, water-body characteristics (e.g., size), and atmospheric conditions. A further limitation is the reliance on purely statistical alignment, which lacks physical, or hydrological context, as it typically excludes ancillary environmental data. This is important because variables such as Precipitation (P), Temperature (T), and Evapotranspiration (E) are not only key drivers of WSE dynamics but also influence the accuracy of WSE_{alt} by affecting signal along its travel path in the atmosphere (Kraemer et al., 2020). Incorporating such environmental variables can help account for both environment-induced measurement errors and natural WSE fluctuations in multi-mission monitoring efforts.

Another shortcoming of previous bias correction approaches is their reliance on linear models, which struggle to capture the nonlinear spatiotemporally dynamic nature of inter- and intra-mission biases (Nielsen et al., 2022). In this context, Deep Learning (DL), as an advanced Machine Learning (ML) technique, offers a promising alternative. DL models are capable of learning complex, nonlinear relationships directly from data and can accommodate diverse and heterogeneous input features. Compared to conventional ML methods, DL models, especially Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architectures, excel at modeling temporal sequences and learning long-range dependencies in time series data (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997). These capabilities have led to their growing adoption in RS and hydrological applications (Zhao et al., 2024).

In this study, a multi-mission synergy of S3, S6, and SWOT data to monitor WSE variations in inland SWRs is conducted for the first time. To enable continuous WSE monitoring across these missions, a DL-based method was developed to correct both inter- and intra-mission biases in WSE_{alt} . To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to use DL models to integrate multiple satellite altimeters for WSE monitoring. The proposed method, the Environmentally Informed LSTM-based Neural Network (EILSTMNet), integrates multi-mission satellite altimetry observations (S3, S6, and SWOT) with environmental variables, P, T, and E, to produce bias-corrected WSE measurements ($WSE_{EILSTMNet}$). Prior studies did not incorporate environmental variables when correcting altimetric biases for multi-mission monitoring of WSE. The proposed approach was evaluated over three lakes, namely Michigan, Ontario, and Winnebago, using four in-situ gauge stations to assess EILSTMNet's performance in generating bias-corrected WSE time series from multi-mission altimetric inputs.

2. Study areas and datasets

2.1. Study areas

This study focuses on three inland lakes in northern United States: Lake Michigan, Lake Ontario, and Lake Winnebago (Fig. 1). We selected these lakes because the measurement accuracy of WSE from different satellite radar altimeters can vary among lakes due to differences in lake characteristics such as size, north-south or west-east orientation, shoreline complexity, and circularity (Kossieris et al., 2024). Accordingly, the selected lakes exhibit contrasting characteristics; for example, in terms of size (Lake Winnebago: ~ 557 km², Lake Ontario: $\sim 19,000$ km², and Lake Michigan: $\sim 58,000$ km²) and orientation, with Lake Ontario oriented west-east and the other two predominantly north-south, making them a valuable testbed for evaluating the proposed multi-mission WSE monitoring methodology. In addition, all three lakes contain in-situ gauging stations and are covered by all three satellite altimetry missions (S3, S6, and SWOT). It should be highlighted that these lakes play a vital role in supporting drinking water supply, agriculture, transportation, commercial shipping, fisheries, and recreational activities (Cherkauer and Sinha, 2010). Hence, understanding WSE dynamics in these lakes is essential.

2.2. Datasets (section S1 of supplementary material provides more details)

Supplementary material (Section S1) provides a more detailed description of the utilized datasets. This study used data from the 20-Hz "enhanced measurement" Level-2 Non-Time-Critical (NTC) products of S3 (both S3A and S3B), 20-Hz standard measurements of High-Resolution (HR) Level-2 NTC altimetry products of S6, and the Level-2 HR Pixel Cloud product (SWOT_L2_HR_PIXC) of SWOT missions as satellite altimetric observations of WSE. In this paper, S3A and S3B were treated as separate altimetry datasets due to their distinct ground tracks, acquisition times, and, consequently, differing atmospheric corrections, all of which can influence their individual performance as well as their inter- and intra-mission biases (Frery et al., 2020). The utilized ground tracks of each mission

Table 1

Summary of the four United States Geological Survey (USGS) in-situ gauge stations (downloadable from <https://waterdata.usgs.gov/>, last accessed June 2025) and the corresponding closest satellite ground tracks.

Station	Lake	Station number	Location (lat, lon)	1st available observation	Temporal frequency (min)	Satellite ground tracks (Fig. 1)			
						S3A	S3B	S6	SWOT
W	Winnebago	04082500	44.0097, -88.5273	2007-10-01	15	549	508	219	466 (left track)
M	Michigan	04087440	41.8892, -87.6079	2007-10-01	1	622	663	041	509 (right track)
O1	Ontario	04219796	43.3752, -78.4864	2017-07-14	6	108	263	228	354 (left track)
O2		0423205342	43.2669, -77.4339	2019-10-18	6	222	377	015	354 (right track)

nearest to each in-situ gauge station in all study areas are shown in Fig. 1 and summarized in Table 1. For each SWOT overpass, two footprints are available to the left and right of nadir, and the footprint nearest to the corresponding in-situ gauge station was used in the analysis. All available data from different altimetry missions over the three study lakes, from the first satellite acquisition coincident with WSE_{in-situ} measurements to the end of 2024, were included in the analysis.

Environmental variables (P, T, and E) were also obtained from the ERA5 dataset. Specifically, the daily aggregated ERA5 product with a spatial resolution of 11 km was used through Google Earth Engine (GEE). To spatially average daily environmental variables of P, T, and E, basin boundaries derived from the freely available HydroBASINS dataset were also used (Lehner and Grill, 2013). This approach yields one daily value per environmental variable for each station.

Moreover, measurements of WSE_{in-situ} from four in-situ gauge stations (one station in Lake Winnebago [hereafter W], one in Lake Michigan [M], and two in Lake Ontario [O1 and O2]) were used as reference data. Detailed information about each station is summarized in Table 1. For consistency with satellite altimetry data, all WSE_{in-situ} values were transformed into a common vertical datum: the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) (see Section 3.1.1 for details).

3. Methodology

The proposed methodology consists of two main phases: (1) Dataset preparation and (2) Model development and evaluation.

3.1. Dataset preparation

3.1.1. Static inputs of EILSTMNet

Initially, WSE_{alt} values must be prepared separately for each satellite altimeter (S3A, S3B, S6, and SWOT). During data acquisition, these satellites collect thousands of measurements over both land and water surfaces. These measurement points, known as Virtual Stations (VS), must be filtered to retain only those located entirely within the target water bodies. To accomplish this, non-water observations are excluded using the Joint Research Center (JRC) permanent water mask (Pekel et al., 2016). This filtering process is applied consistently across all satellite datasets (S3A, S3B, S6, and SWOT) for each lake, resulting in a set of on-water VS per satellite pass. Then, for S3A, S3B, and S6, WSE of each VS is computed using the satellite-measured range derived from the Offset Center of Gravity (OCOG) retracking algorithm (Jiang et al., 2020). Although multiple retracking algorithms are typically available within each mission's data product, OCOG has demonstrated superior performance over inland water bodies due to its robustness in handling complex waveforms (Gao et al., 2019). The WSE for each VS is calculated using Equation (1):

$$WSE = H - (R + Corr) \tag{1}$$

where H is the satellite altitude, R is the retracked range, and Corr represents the sum of geophysical and atmospheric corrections (M. Jiang et al., 2023). It should be highlighted that the SWOT product used in this study (Section S1.3 of the supplementary material) provides WSE_{alt} estimates. After filtering on-water VS in the SWOT data, only points with a quality flag of “good” were retained (Maubant et al., 2025). To ensure consistency across all data sources (altimetry and in-situ gauge data), the WSE_{alt} at each VS is transformed from geoid heights to ellipsoidal heights referenced to the WGS84 datum. Finally, for each satellite pass, the median WSE_{alt} value across all valid VS points is retained as the representative WSE_{alt}.

Fig. 2. Temporal distribution of satellite observations (S3A, S3B, S6, and SWOT) across each in-situ gauge station. N denotes the number of observations with corresponding available WSE_{in-situ} measurements.

Fig. 2 displays the temporal distribution and total number of each satellite observation that coincide with $WSE_{in-situ}$ measurements. In total, 246 observations were available for W, 263 for M, 220 for O1, and 207 for O2. Compared with 2016–2017, when WSE observations relied primarily on S3A with a 27-day repeat cycle, combining multiple altimeter missions reduces the revisit interval to approximately 5 days in 2024.

Each WSE_{alt} is paired with its corresponding Day of Year (DOY) and a satellite-specific identifier. DOY enables the model to capture seasonality and temporal context, while the satellite identifier allows it to account for satellite-specific characteristics. DOY was encoded as a circular variable, using $DOY_{sin} = \sin(2\pi \times DOY/365)$, and $DOY_{cos} = \cos(2\pi \times DOY/365)$. This maps the annual cycle onto the unit circle so that December 31 and January 1 are close in feature space, avoiding the artificial discontinuity introduced by treating DOY as a scalar (1–365). Satellite identifiers were also represented with one-hot vectors to avoid imposing an ordinal relationship that would arise from integer coding (e.g., 0, 1, 2, 3). By identifying the satellite source of each WSE_{alt} measurement, the model can learn to correct both inter-mission and intra-mission biases more effectively. WSE_{alt} , DOY, and satellite identifiers are the static inputs to the EILSTMNet model.

3.1.2. Time series inputs of EILSTMNet

As mentioned earlier, the proposed network is environmentally informed. Therefore, for each WSE_{alt} , the time series of daily P, T, and E are included as inputs to the EILSTMNet model. A time series of environmental variables is used instead of a single-day value or a fixed-window average because they have delayed or cumulative effects, which must be captured to improve model accuracy (Konapala et al., 2020). For each computed WSE_{alt} , a corresponding time series of P, T, and E values is prepared based on its acquisition date. Specifically, a window of τ days is applied, extending backward from the observation date. For example, for $\tau = 30$ days, if a WSE_{alt} observation is recorded on March 1, 2024, the model ingests P, T, and E data from February 1 to March 1, 2024, forming a 30-day backward-looking time series aligned with the observation. The best value for τ is determined as explained in Section 3.2.3.

Fig. 3. (a–c) Distribution of coincident $WSE_{in-situ}$ values corresponding to satellite observations. Stations O1 and O2 are shown on a single panel due to their similar ranges. (d) Distribution of ΔWSE , defined as $\Delta WSE = WSE_{in-situ} - WSE_{alt}$, across all stations. μ and σ represent the mean and standard deviation of the fitted Gaussian curve, respectively. N indicates the total number of observations.

3.1.3. Target parameter of EILSTMNet

For each training sample, comprising a time series of environmental variables and associated static inputs, a corresponding target output is required to train and validate the EILSTMNet model. As shown in Fig. 3a–c, the $WSE_{in-situ}$ values vary substantially across the stations: approximately 227 m for W, 176 m for M, and 75 m for O1 and O2. This large variation results in a highly imbalanced target distribution if the model were trained to directly predict $WSE_{in-situ}$, which could negatively affect model performance (Dehkordi et al., 2024). While it is technically possible to train separate models for each station, this would be computationally inefficient and limited by the small number of available samples per station. To overcome these limitations, this study adopts ΔWSE as the target parameter, defined as $\Delta WSE = WSE_{in-situ} - WSE_{alt}$. As illustrated in Fig. 3d, the distribution of ΔWSE across all stations is approximately Gaussian, which not only results in a more balanced and model-friendly target distribution but also enables the EILSTMNet model to be trained on a dataset of 936 samples. This unified modeling approach enhances generalization across diverse lake conditions and eliminates the need to train separate models.

3.1.4. Preprocessing

In this phase, WSE_{alt} , the time-series variables (P, T, and E), and the target parameter (ΔWSE) were standardized using median centering and scaling based on the interquartile range. Subsequently, normalization was applied to rescale all values to a range between 0 and 1. These preprocessing steps help prevent any individual feature or variable from disproportionately influencing the model due to differences in numerical scale (Dehkordi et al., 2024). For evaluation, the model predictions were converted back to the original scale.

Fig. 4. (a) Architecture of the proposed EILSTMNet. (b) Internal structure of an LSTM cell.

3.2. Model development and evaluation

The proposed EILSTMNet (Fig. 4a) consists of two main blocks: 1) an LSTM block for learning from time series of environmental variables, and 2) a Fully Connected Neural Network (FCNN) block for integrating LSTM module with static features.

3.2.1. LSTM block

LSTM models, a type of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), are specifically designed to learn temporal dependencies in data by introducing gating mechanisms that control the flow of information over time (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997). Unlike simple RNNs, which suffer from issues like vanishing or exploding gradients, LSTMs maintain more stable memory dynamics through a combination of input (i), forget (f), and output (o) gates. At each time step t , the LSTM cell receives the current input vector (x_t), along with the previous hidden state (h_{t-1}) and cell state (c_{t-1}) (Fig. 4b). In a stacked LSTM, the hidden state h_t from one layer serves as the input x_t to the next layer. It then updates the current states (h_t, c_t) using a set of processes summarized in Equation (2).

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_t &= \sigma(W_{ii} \times x_t + b_{ii} + W_{hi} \times h_{t-1} + b_{hi}) \\
 f_t &= \sigma(W_{if} \times x_t + b_{if} + W_{hf} \times h_{t-1} + b_{hf}) \\
 o_t &= \sigma(W_{io} \times x_t + b_{io} + W_{ho} \times h_{t-1} + b_{ho}) \\
 c^* t &= \tanh(W_{ic} \times x_t + b_{ic} + W_{hc} \times h_{t-1} + b_{hc}) \\
 c_t &= f_t \circ c_{t-1} + i_t \circ c^* t \\
 h_t &= o_t \circ \tanh(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where σ denotes the sigmoid activation function, \circ is the Hadamard product, W and b represent the weights and biases for each gate (learned during training), and $c^* t$ is the temporary cell state. Initial hidden and cell states of the k th layer (h_0^k, c_0^k) are set to zeros. Each LSTM layer can have a different number of hidden units (expressed as $\text{size}(h^k)$), allowing the network to learn hierarchical temporal features at varying levels of abstraction. The weights and biases (W and b) in each gate are shared across time steps but not across layers.

3.2.2. FCNN block

The final hidden state h_t^k of LSTM block (where k denotes the last LSTM layer and t is the final time step) effectively summarizes the entire environmental time series in a high-level representation. It is then concatenated with the static features: WSE_{alt} , satellite identifier, and DOY (see Section 3.1.1) to form the inputs of FCNN block as a concatenated vector ($z^0 = [h_t^k, x_{\text{static}}]$). The FCNN consists of multiple layers (m), where each hidden layer performs a transformation using the ReLU activation function based on Equation (3) where i is the layer number, W^i and b^i are the weights and biases of i th layer with p_i neurons (Fig. 4a).

$$z^i = \text{ReLU}(W^i z^{i-1} + b^i), i = 1, \dots, m-1 \tag{3}$$

The final output (ΔWSE) is estimated in the last output layer by $\Delta\text{WSE} = W^m z^{m-1} + b^m$. Using this correction, the final corrected WSE is obtained as: $\text{WSE}_{\text{EILSTMNet}} = \text{WSE}_{\text{alt}} + \Delta\text{WSE}$.

3.2.3. Hyperparameter tuning, training and evaluation

To reduce the risk of overfitting, dropout regularization with a dropout rate of 0.1 was applied to each LSTM layer (excluding the final one) and to all FCNN layers (except the output layer) during training (Srivastava et al., 2014). Adam was used as the optimizer of the model with the Mean Squared Error (MSE) as the loss function (Ruder, 2016). Training was conducted for 200 epochs using PyTorch library in Python.

From the prepared reference dataset, all samples from the last six months (after 2024-06-01, $N = 148$) were excluded as a holdout set from all steps related to tuning and training. The holdout length was fixed at six months, as extending it further would reduce the number of available SWOT observations in the final dataset. Then, 50% random of the remaining samples ($N = 788$) were used for hyperparameter selection via 5-fold cross-validation with a grid search (Table 2). All combinations of the hyperparameter search space were evaluated, and the configuration yielding the lowest average Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) between $\text{WSE}_{\text{EILSTMNet}}$ and $\text{WSE}_{\text{in-situ}}$ across folds was selected. Once the optimal parameters were identified, Leave-One-Sample-Out (LOSO) method was conducted for final performance evaluation of the model. Although computationally intensive, LOSO allows each sample to be used for both training and testing, thereby maximizing data utilization (Vehtari et al., 2017). Moreover, LOSO provides an almost unbiased estimate of the

Table 2

Hyperparameter search space and their optimal values for the proposed EILSTMNet model.

Parameter	Search Space	Optimal values
τ (length of input environmental variables in days)	[5, 10, 15, 30, 45, 90, 120]	30
LSTM layers and hidden state size of each layer	$[h^1, h^2, \dots, h^k], k \in [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]$ and $h^i \in [64, 32, 16, 8]$	[32, 16]
FCN layers and number of neurons in each layer	$[p_1, \dots, p_m], m \in [1, 2, 3]$ and $p_m \in [64, 32, 16, 8, 4]$	[32, 8, 4]
Learning rate	[0.0005, 0.0001, 0.005, 0.001, 0.05, 0.01]	0.001
Batch size	[256, 128, 64, 32, 16, 8]	64

model's generalization performance, as the model is evaluated across all possible single-sample test cases, and it enables the reconstruction of a time series of WSE measurements. To assess temporal transferability, the model with the selected hyperparameters was trained on all 788 pre-holdout samples and tested on the holdout period ($N = 148$). The EILSTMNet estimates for both scenarios were compared against $WSE_{in-situ}$ using RMSE and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC). Moreover, to characterize the two-dimensional scatter in the WSE_{alt} vs. $WSE_{in-situ}$ and $WSE_{EILSTMNet}$ vs. $WSE_{in-situ}$, the area of the Bivariate Confidence Ellipse (BCE) was used, which is largely robust to extreme outliers as it encloses 95% of all points (Schubert and Kirchner, 2014). A large BCE area indicates a widely dispersed cloud, whereas a small area denotes a tight cluster of points near the 1:1 line.

To assess the contribution of environmental variables, the EILSTMNet model with all three inputs (P, T, and E) was compared to simplified variants using only one variable (EILSTMNet-P, EILSTMNet-T, and EILSTMNet-E). Additionally, a version using only static features in the FCNN block (denoted FCNN-static) was evaluated to quantify the added value of environmental inputs. For architectural comparison, the LSTM block was replaced with a 1D Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN) having the same number of layers as the LSTM block (Li et al., 2021). Each CNN layer used a kernel size of 3 with max-pooling with stride = 1, and the number of filters matched the hidden size of the corresponding LSTM layer. The final CNN output was concatenated with static features and passed through the same FCNN as in EILSTMNet. This model is referred to as EICNNNet in the results. Moreover, the performance of the EILSTMNet model was compared with a widely used correction method, known as 'average bias removal', where the differences between the mean WSE_{alt} values of other missions and that of the best-performing mission (based on RMSE and PCC) were calculated and removed to align all missions to a common reference for each station (Feng et al., 2023; L. Jiang et al., 2023). The selected baseline satellites were: S6 for W, S3A for M, S6 for O1, and S6 for O2. SWOT was not used as the baseline for O2 due to limited temporal overlap with S3A and S3B.

4. Results

4.1. EILSTMNet performance

For the best hyperparameters summarized in Table 2, the impact of different values of τ is shown in Fig. 5. As the τ increases, the average RMSE and PCC across folds improve, reaching their best values at $\tau = 30$ days (RMSE = 0.07 m; PCC = 0.94). Increasing τ beyond 30 days does not further enhance performance and the results remain relatively stable while the number of model parameters grows due to a longer input. Therefore, $\tau = 30$ days was selected as the optimal window length. For the remainder of the paper, EILSTMNet refers to the model with $\tau = 30$ days and the hyperparameters listed in Table 2.

Fig. 6 compares the multi-mission WSE_{alt} and $WSE_{EILSTMNet}$ with $WSE_{in-situ}$ using scatter plots derived from LOSO validation (see Section 3.2.3). The RMSE and PCC values show that the multi-mission WSE_{alt} measurements have RMSEs of 0.30, 0.20, 0.37, and 0.39 m at stations W, M, O1, and O2, respectively, while the corresponding PCCs are 0.54, 0.89, 0.66, and 0.65. After applying EILSTMNet, the accuracy improves markedly: RMSE decreases to ≤ 0.11 m, and PCC rises to > 0.90 at all stations. The point clouds in the scatter plots also become more tightly clustered around the 1:1 line, which is reflected in the BCE values. The temporal curves of WSE in Fig. 7 further confirm that multi-mission WSE_{alt} trends before bias correction show clear misalignments with the corresponding $WSE_{in-situ}$

Fig. 5. Impact of the input environmental time-series length (τ) on EILSTMNet performance (hyperparameters in Table 2), based on the average (a) RMSE and (b) PCC from 5-fold cross-validation for hyperparameter tuning.

Fig. 6. Point-by-point comparison of multi-mission altimeter (a) WSE_{alt} and (b) $WSE_{EILSTMNet}$ with $WSE_{in-situ}$ across all stations using LOSO validation. RMSE values are reported in meters (m).

observations, whereas the $WSE_{EILSTMNet}$ values closely follow the seasonal patterns and peaks of the in-situ data.

Scatterplots comparing WSE_{alt} and $WSE_{EILSTMNet}$ with $WSE_{in-situ}$ are shown in Fig. 8 for each individual satellite altimeter. These results also demonstrate substantial improvements in $WSE_{EILSTMNet}$ compared to WSE_{alt} . For instance, at sites W, M, O1, and O2, SWOT's RMSE decreases from 0.28, 0.56, 0.15, and 0.12 m to 0.18, 0.12, 0.08, and 0.10 m, respectively. Satellite-specific temporal curves (Fig. S1–S4 in the supplementary material) show the same improvements.

Fig. 7. Temporal WSE curves comparison, across all stations, between (a) WSE_{alt} and (b) WSE_{EILSTMNet} versus WSE_{in-situ}. The WSE_{EILSTMNet} curves are derived using LOSO validation.

4.2. Temporal transferability

Fig. 9 evaluates the temporal transferability of the EILSTMNet model (see Section 3.2.3). The results demonstrate that EILSTMNet generalizes well to unseen future data across all stations. Specifically, the model is not only temporally transferable, but also consistently produces more accurate WSE estimates than the WSE_{alt} for the same period. For example, at site M, WSE_{alt} measurements give an RMSE of 0.29 m and a PCC of 0.64 against WSE_{in-situ}, whereas WSE_{EILSTMNet}, despite not being trained on data from this period, achieved a significantly lower RMSE of 0.08 m and a higher PCC of 0.88. Furthermore, the temporal curve of WSE_{EILSTMNet} closely follows the WSE_{in-situ} with minimal offsets, capturing both seasonal variations and trends accurately.

4.3. Comparison to other methods

In this section, the performance of other methods (Table 3) is compared with EILSTMNet (see Section 3.2.3) using LOSO against WSE_{in-situ} values of all four in-situ gauge stations. The initial WSE_{alt} without applying any corrections yielded an average RMSE of 0.31 m and a PCC of 0.69. The widely used correction method in the literature (average bias removal) failed to outperform EILSTMNet. Utilizing only the FCNN block of EILSTMNet, without incorporating environmental variables, led to modest improvements reducing the RMSE to 0.21 m and increasing the PCC to 0.78. The inclusion of individual environmental variables enhanced model performance, with EILSTMNet-E achieving the best results among the single-variable cases (RMSE: 0.13 m, PCC: 0.86). Notably, the proposed

Fig. 8. Comparison of satellite-specific (a) WSE_{ait} and (b) $WSE_{EILSTMNet}$ against $WSE_{in-situ}$ across all locations. All RMSE values are reported in meters.

EILSTMNet, which incorporates all three variables (P, T, and E) achieved the lowest RMSE (0.09 m) and the highest PCC (0.93), marking it as the most effective configuration. Replacing the LSTM block in EILSTMNet with a 1D-CNN (EICNNNet) led to a reduced performance (RMSE: 0.14 m, PCC: 0.81).

5. Discussion

This study examined the synergistic use of S3, S6, and SWOT altimetric missions for monitoring inland WSE. As shown in Fig. 2, compared with 2016–2017, when WSE observations relied primarily on S3A with a 27-day repeat cycle, combining multiple altimeter missions reduces the revisit interval to approximately 5 days in 2024, underscoring the importance of multi-mission integration for WSE monitoring.

Despite the improved temporal frequency of WSE observations, multi-mission integration was limited by the presence of both intra- and inter-mission biases. As illustrated in Fig. 8a, intra-mission biases were evident in the scatterplots of WSE_{ait} versus $WSE_{in-situ}$,

Fig. 9. Temporal transferability assessment of the EILSTMNet model, trained with data up to 2024-05-31 and evaluated with data from 2024 to 06-01 to the end of 2024.

where the point clouds were broadly dispersed rather than tightly clustered along the 1:1 line. This spread reflected inconsistencies between consecutive passes of the same satellite over the same location, which mostly stems from: (1) temporal variability in atmospheric conditions (Fernandes et al., 2014), and (2) data maturity due to mission-specific calibration stages (Biancamaria et al., 2016). The intra-mission bias was also spatially variable. For example, S3B showed a positive bias at station M but negative biases at O1 and O2 (Fig. 8a). This spatial variability could be the result from local lake characteristics such as surface area, morphology, or surrounding terrain, all of which can influence altimetric measurement accuracy (Busker et al., 2019; Shu et al., 2020). These temporal and spatial variabilities in intra-mission biases cannot be addressed by conventional correction strategies such as average bias removal, as depicted in Table 3 (Feng et al., 2023; L. Jiang et al., 2023).

Inter-mission biases were similarly problematic. As shown in Fig. 6a, merging WSE_{alt} data from all missions resulted in a larger BCE compared to that of any individual single-satellite at each location, indicating that inter-mission biases were added to the existing

Table 3

Performance comparison of EILSTMNet with other methods using LOSO against all the $WSE_{in-situ}$ values of all four in-situ gauge stations.

Scenario	RMSE [m]	PCC
Altimetry (No improvements)	0.31	0.69
Average bias removal	0.29	0.72
FCNN-static	0.21	0.78
EILSTMNet-P	0.15	0.81
EILSTMNet-T	0.16	0.80
EILSTMNet-E	0.13	0.86
EICNNNet (P, T, E)	0.14	0.81
EILSTMNet (P, T, E)	0.09	0.93

intra-mission biases. Temporal curve plots (Figs. 7 and 9a) further confirmed this: abrupt shifts often coincided with satellite transitions. The magnitude and direction of these shifts vary across locations and over time, further revealing the complex, non-stationary nature of inter-mission biases (Ričko et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2011).

Given the complexities of both intra- and inter-mission biases, EILSTMNet was designed to simultaneously address both intra- and inter-mission biases. The effectiveness of EILSTMNet was clearly obvious where the scatter point clouds became tightly aligned with the 1:1 line in single-satellite scenarios (Fig. 8b). Moreover, there was a significant reduction in the BCE values in multi-mission scenarios compared to the maximum single-satellite BCE values (Fig. 6b). These results confirm that EILSTMNet was capable of learning and correcting variable intra- and inter-mission biases, enabling more consistent multi-mission WSE monitoring.

The inclusion of environmental variables (P, T, and E) played a crucial role in enhancing model performance. As shown in Table 3, removing these inputs led to increased RMSE and reduced PCC. These variables capture both the hydrological drivers of WSE dynamics and the atmospheric conditions that influence altimetric signal propagation, providing valuable context for improving accuracy (Kraemer et al., 2020). Architecturally, the proposed model's LSTM-based sequence modeling was compared with a 1D-CNN-based alternative. While 1D-CNNs are commonly used for modeling sequential data, EILSTMNet's LSTM-based architecture outperformed them due to its superior ability to capture long-term temporal dependencies an area where CNNs are often limited because of their limited receptive fields (Alzubaidi et al., 2021).

Finally, the model's temporal transferability was evaluated through a six-month hold-out test (Fig. 9). EILSTMNet successfully improved WSE_{alt} measurements during this unseen period, achieving high accuracy despite not being trained on that portion of the data. This demonstrated the model's robustness and practical value: once trained, EILSTMNet can be applied to future satellite WSE estimations without requiring new in-situ observations for recalibration.

It should be noted that the dataset used in this study consisted of 936 samples. Several factors support its adequacy for training the proposed EILSTMNet model. The optimal model architecture (Table 2) resulted in a lightweight network comprising only two LSTM layers with 32 and 16 hidden units, respectively, making it well suited for learning from moderately sized datasets. To further ensure robust model training and evaluation, a rigorous multi-stage validation framework was employed. Hyperparameters were optimized using 5-fold cross-validation, followed by a LOSO cross-validation strategy (Figs. 6 and 7), which provided an almost unbiased estimate of generalization performance. In addition, the model's temporal transferability was assessed using an independent holdout period (Fig. 9), allowing evaluation under unseen temporal conditions. The strong performance observed in both the LOSO validation, and the temporally independent testing indicates that the model learned generalizable patterns rather than memorizing the training data, demonstrating that the available sample size was sufficient for reliable multi-mission WSE monitoring using satellite radar altimeters and the proposed EILSTMNet model.

The proposed EILSTMNet model is, in principle, applicable to other regions worldwide, as it relies on globally available satellite altimetry missions (S3, S6, and SWOT) and widely used gridded environmental datasets such as ERA5. The model architecture itself is not tied to specific absolute values of P, T, and E. Instead, these variables are used as auxiliary inputs whose temporal patterns are learned by the LSTM block to extract high-level features, which are then combined with static inputs through the FCNN block. The model is trained end-to-end to learn relationships between environmental time series, satellite-specific characteristics, and values of bias correction in a data-driven manner. This design supports transferability across regions where the absolute ranges of P, T, and E may differ, but their temporal relationships with WSE dynamics remain informative. Nonetheless, the strong temporal generalization observed in this study indicates that EILSTMNet provides a flexible and extensible framework for multi-mission WSE monitoring across diverse geographic regions. In this study, the combined use of P, T, and E resulted in the best performance (Table 3). That said, how much the relative importance and combined influence of P, T, and E vary across different hydroclimatic regimes requires further investigation in other geographical locations.

6. Conclusion

Multi-mission RS of WSE enhances the temporal frequency of WSE observations. However, the synergistic use of several satellite altimetry missions is hindered by inter- and intra-mission biases. This study introduced EILSTMNet, a DL-based model developed to overcome these biases and to combine S3, S6, and SWOT. By leveraging stacked LSTM layers, EILSTMNet effectively captured temporal sequences of environmental variables and integrated them with static satellite-derived features through an FCNN block. The model demonstrated significant improvements in correcting satellite-derived WSE estimates, achieving strong agreement with in-situ

gauge measurements across different lakes. Moreover, EILSTMNet exhibited robust temporal generalization, highlighting its potential to be applied to future unseen periods without the need for additional gauge data once trained. Overall, EILSTMNet provides a promising solution for the fusion of multi-mission altimetry datasets, offering enhanced accuracy and continuity in inland WSE monitoring and supporting improved hydrological modeling and water resource management.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mahdis Rezapour: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Alireza Taheri Dehkordi:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Mohammad Javad Valadan Zoej:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Elahe Khesali:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Amir Naghibi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Hossein Hashemi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Ethical statement

We, the authors of the manuscript titled “Enhanced Multi-mission Remote Sensing of Inland Water Surface Elevation Using Sentinel-3, Sentinel-6, and SWOT Satellite Altimeters and an Environmentally Informed LSTM-based Neural Network,” confirm that this work adheres to the highest ethical standards in research and visualization, and writing. Moreover, we confirm that this paper is the author's own original work, which has not been previously published elsewhere. Please feel free to contact us with any further questions or concerns.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsase.2026.102019>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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